

PEDAGOGICAL PROCESS MODEL AIMED AT DEVELOPING THE ARTISTIC AND AESTHETIC TASTE OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS THROUGH MUSIC

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Annotation: This article talks about the model of the pedagogical process aimed at developing the artistic and aesthetic taste of elementary school students through music.

Keywords: intuition, aesthetic taste, faith, spiritual education, musical genre.

Pedagogical tools - include material objects and objects of spiritual culture designed for the organization and implementation of the pedagogical process.

According to D.N. Zarin, such unique musical instruments are musical genres . "Three whales" in music - song, dance, march. These three most common democratic genres are the easiest way to get into the art of music. It is they that make it possible to "study" the musical and life experience of children as the first generalization at the empirical level .

Musical genre is a multi-valued concept that describes historically formed generations and types in connection with the origin and life purpose of musical works, the method and conditions (place) of performance and perception, as well as their content and characteristics form .

The complexity and uncertainty of the concept of "musical genre" is due to the fact that all the factors determining it do not act simultaneously and with equal force. These factors themselves are in a different order (for example, the form and place of execution) and can act in different combinations with different degrees of interdependence. That is why different classification systems of music genres have been developed in music science .

For a long time, attempts to classify musical genres have become a natural extension and addition to the description of genres themselves. In modern musicology, special attention is paid to the problems of classification.

It is appropriate to start a brief review of classifications according to their chronological principle with the description of the typology of genres proposed by the German musicologist G. Bessler .

Analyzing the relationship of music with its forms of existence and vital functions, he promoted and justified the division of all genres into presented and everyday genres in a number of his studies. In fact, music in a public concert, like in an opera house, is presented to the audience as an artistic aesthetic value, and therefore it can be called a presentation. A distinctive feature of a public concert as a presented music genre is the opposition of performers and listeners, and the audience of the concert hall represents a unique unit - the audience. On the contrary, genres related to church life, festivals and carnivals can be considered on a daily basis. Bessler includes dances, marches, work songs, holiday music, service, ritual genres as everyday music .

The features of musical life in various genres noted by G. Bessler were also thoroughly reviewed and analyzed by other researchers.

In the study of T.V. Popova and in the collective monograph created on his initiative, two main criteria were adopted as the basis for the theory of genres and their classification, as in the work of his German predecessor: music and the conditions for the existence of music. performance characteristics. According to the selected criteria, six groups were identified in the collection of all musical genres:

1. folk - everyday music of oral creativity (songs and instruments);
2. light household and pop entertainment music - music for solo, ensemble, vocal, instrumental, jazz, brass ensembles;
3. chamber music for small halls, soloists and small ensembles;
4. symphonic music performed by large orchestras in concert halls;
5. choral music;
6. musical theater and dramatic works intended for performance on stage .

In conclusion, all these components of the artistic-aesthetic education system are interconnected. The tasks of aesthetic education are leading among them. They predetermine the content of this aspect of the educational process, the types of activities in which this content is most often implemented, and the tools to be used in this case. It also defines the methods of aesthetic education as a specific combination of teacher and student activities, which gives the greatest opportunities for solving them .

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